

**ENVIRONMENTAL
PHYSICS
GROUP**

NEWSLETTER NO 3

JANUARY 1992

THE INSTITUTE OF PHYSICS

Environmental Physics Group Steering Committee

Name	Institution (principal area of interest)
Dr R A Coffee	ICI (applied technology)
Dr Peter Dagley	University of Liverpool (geophysics)
Professor J E Harries	Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (atmospheric science)
Mr Peter Hughes	Kingsway College (education)
Dr Alastair McCartney	Rothamsted Experimental Station (ecology)
Dr Wyn Morgan	Queen Elizabeth Medical Centre (medical physics)
Dr Douglas Peirson	recently retired from Harwell (physical models of environmental processes)
Dr David Pugh	IOSDL (oceanographic science)
Dr Ranjeet Sokhi	DTI Warren Spring Laboratory (inland and coastal aquatic systems)
Dr John Stewart	Institute of Hydrology (fluids)
Professor Michael Unsworth	University of Nottingham (agriculture and global impact)
Ms Susanna Lithiby	Public Affairs Dept. IOP (public awareness)

Useful addresses

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STEERING COMMITTEE NEWS

The Steering Committee has met on two occasions September and 29 November

The Steering Committee welcomed the publication of the *Environmental Physics - Courses in Higher Education* booklet by the Institute. Available by sending an SAE to the Education department, the booklet gives up to date information on where a student studying physics in the sixth form can continue onto study a course in higher education with an environmental physics component. In the light of the multidisciplinary nature of the subject, the net was extended to include all science departments. The booklet also gives an indication of what courses are being developed to offer at a later date.

With a foreword by Peter Hughes, Chair of the EPG's Education Sub-Committee, this marks the first important step in raising the awareness of environmental physics in higher education. The next logical step is to let physics undergraduates know of the opportunities available once they have graduated. The Steering Committee feels one way it can tackle this is to compile a specially selected list of scientists involved in environmental physics research who would be happy to speak to groups of students. This list can then be circulated to student physical societies, and Institute reps in Higher Education.

The EPG's first AGM

It is intended to hold the group's first AGM in early March. A call for nominations to the Committee will go out in January. The three key positions will be Chair, ViceChair, and Honorary Secretary. The majority of the existing Steering Committee has agreed to stand for election. It was decided to use occasion of the AGM as an opportunity to have a keynote lecture from a leading practitioner in the field. Details will be circulated with the call for nominations.

Membership of the group now stands at 280 with some adjustments expected as IOP members decide which groups to subscribe to as they return their 1992 subscription notices.

Database of members' interests

Thank you to all those who replied to our request for information for the members' database. The information is now being collated and a report will be included in the next newsletter. Any members still wishing to send their forms in are welcome to do so. Dr Sokhi has recently moved to: DTI Warren Spring Laboratories, Gunned Wood Road, Stevenage SG1 2BX

The Steering Committee is proposing to the Council of the Institute of Physics that it become a "parent" member of JAG, the Joint Association for Geophysicists. Having deliberated this at some length in Steering Committee Meetings, and mindful of the wish for geophysicists who are IOP members to become part of JAG, we are looking forward to a resolution of this issue. In recent years JAG has been given further responsibilities by bodies such as the Royal Society, thus recognising it as the UK voice for geophysicists.

The next issue of the newsletter will be compiled during March for publication after the AGM. All contributions welcome.

NB: this is the last copy of the newsletter to be distributed free to non-members of the Institute. IOP non-members can request membership information on enclosed form. In many cases, subscriber may be the most appropriate type of membership. This entitles members to participate and be kept informed about the activities of a certain group without needing full IOP membership.

Susanna Lithiby

PROGRAMME HIGHLIGHTS

SUMMER VISIT TO THE UNIVERSITY OF NOTTINGHAM

The Department of Physiology and Environmental Science kindly played host to a visit of EPG members on 26 June. Our thanks go to Dr Clark for organising the day. A summary sheet of the programme is enclosed with this newsletter.

ENERGY FROM THE ENVIRONMENT — THE RENEWABLE ALTERNATIVE

The Environmental Physics Group held its second major meeting with the Challenger Society and the Royal Meteorological Society. Many thanks go to all the speakers, both these groups and the two organisers, Dr David Pugh and Dr John Stewart, for providing a very stimulating day. The meeting was packed and Steering Committee members were delighted to see so many students among the audience.

The enclosed sheet is an edited version of the rounding up given by Don Lennard at the end of the day, added to from the notes of Dick Dougal and myself.

Don Lennard is Managing Director of D E Lennard & Associates Ltd, an engineering consultancy which specialises in offshore underwater and energy activities. He is currently in charge of the Marine Technology Directorate, and is a long term advocate of Ocean Thermal Energy Conversion. For further information on this or any of his other activities, contact D E Lennard & Associates Ltd, 40 Broxbourne Road, Orpington, Kent BR6 0AY; tel 0689 823634.

NEWS FROM THE INSTITUTE

CSTI activities

The first CSTI Environmental Information paper will be available in January. Entitled *The Greenhouse Effect - Fact or Fiction?*, it is aimed at interested members of the public and students as well as members of the constituent bodies of the CSTI (the Council for Science and Technology Institutes). The paper draws on the expertise of the IOP, the Royal Society of Chemistry, the Institute of Biology and the Geological Society and is intended to sort the fact from the fiction about the greenhouse effect. By focussing on the most commonly confused areas, it is hoped this will contribute to a better public understanding of the complexities surrounding this vital issue.

Copies can be obtained by sending an A4 SAE to the Public Affairs Department.

Dr Ranjeet Sokhi, a member of the EPG Steering Committee has kindly agreed to serve on the CSTI's Advisory Committee on the Environment (ACE). The ACE exists to focus and act on issues that cut across boundaries, particularly ones which affect professional scientists. The other IOP member is Susanna Lithiby, IOP Public Affairs Manager. The Committee is proving a useful way of keeping in touch with developments at a national and European level, for example, the many directives emanating from the EC. Dr Sokhi's appointment will further strengthen links between the CSTI Committee and the EPG.

FUTURE MEETINGS

Where price and registration details are not specified, these will be circulated at a later date. If information required before, please contact the organiser.

Spectroscopy Group of the IOP, in collaboration with the EPB Optical sensing of atmospheric species

18 March 1992, Society of Chemical Industry, London
This meeting will cover recent developments in laser and other optical spectroscopic techniques for measuring gaseous species, including pollutants.
To register: contact IOP Meetings Dept, 47 Belgrave Square, London SW1X 8QX

Joint meeting with the Environmental Maths Group of the Institute of Mathematics and Applications

1 April 1992 University College London

The meeting will focus on careers and research in environmental science. It is targeted at undergraduates and teachers with the aim of opening up the field to show the opportunities available.

Joint organisers: Peter Hughes, Kingsway College, Steve Hobbs, Cranfield Institute of Technology

Edinburgh Science Festival

21 April 1992 Royal Society of Edinburgh
The Steering Committee has been collaborating with the Scottish Branch as they prepare a programme based on renewable energy.

Organiser: Dr Alan Harper, Scottish Branch Chair

Remote sensing from space - early scientific results from ERS-1 and UARS

6 May 1992 Rutherford Appleton Laboratory, Didcot, OXON

Early new results in atmospheric physics, oceanography, cryospheric and land surface processes from the above missions will be discussed. There will be an opportunity for those present to hear and comment on these two groundbreaking missions.

Up to ten half hour presentations will be given, and the programme looks likely to focus on the various instruments and experiments involved and the latest measurements.

Organiser: Professor John Harries, Associate Director APS and Head of Space Science Dept

The following day the Royal Meteorological Society and the Royal Society of Chemistry are sponsoring a meeting organised by Dr R A Cox, NERC on
Arctic Ozone 1992 - first perspective of the BASOE Campaign

Environmental Geophysics

Jointly organised by the EPG and the Environmental and Industrial Geophysics Group of the Joint Association for Geophysics

19 May 1992 British Geological Survey, Keyworth, Nottingham
The meeting is free to members, £10 to non-members and £5 to members. Lunch is not included but will be available in the restaurant at BGS.
Joint Convenor: Dr D McCann, British Geological Survey, Keyworth, NOTTS NG12 5GG

Consideration is also being given to an evening meeting in the Autumn on the various environmental initiatives from the NERC and the SERC

1993 Meetings

Environmental physics in agriculture

date: to be confirmed Rothamstead Experimental Station, Herts

Organiser: Dr Alastair McCartney

Marine pollution (provisional title)

date: to be confirmed Warren Spring Laboratories, Stevenage

OTHER IOP MEETINGS

Plasma Technologies - environmental and manufacturing opportunities

Organised by The Institute of Physics and the Centre for the Exploitation of Science and Technology, with support from sponsors including the EC

February 19 1992 Queen Elizabeth II Conference Centre, London

An international meeting to look at the opportunities to exploit the environmentally clean properties of plasmas, in particular in view of the forthcoming strengthening of EC legislation. This one-day keynote meeting will review trends in the the US, Europe, Japan and the UK.

Contact: The IOP Meetings & Conferences Dept, 47 Belgrave Square, London SW1X 8QX; tel 071 235 6111, fax 071 259 6002

OTHER MEETINGS

UNCED

International Conference on Water and the Environment

26 - 31 January Dublin, Ireland

Contact: Dr G Young, ICVE, c/o WMO Case Postale no 2300, CH-1211 Geneva 2; tel: 4122 730 8275

ERS-1 Products, Development and Initial Results

February date to be confirmed RAE Farnborough

Contact: Dr N McIntyre, Earth Observation Sciences, Branksome Wood Road, Fleet Hants, GU3 8JS; tel: 0252 24461

Royal Society of Chemistry

The Tropospheric Chemistry and Deposition of Nitrogen Species

19 February The Scientific Societies Lecture Theatre, London W1

NO_x emissions from combustion sources play a central role in several of today's major environmental issues, including acid rain and formation of photochemical pollutants. As legislation is reviewed over the next few years it is important that policymakers are provided with clear scientific guidance on which to base their decisions.

This symposium presents a summary of the current knowledge and uncertainties in the atmospheric science linking emissions to effects in today's environmental issues. It will be of interest to research scientists, environmental managers, environmental consultants and policymakers.

Organiser: Dr A T Cocks, National Power PLC, Technology & Environmental Centre
To attend: contact Ms P A Sim, 24 Southfield Drive, Hazlemere, High Wycombe, Bucks HP15 7HB; tel 0494 713664, fax 0494 714516

International Space Year

27 February - 1 March Abingdon, UK

International Symposium on Global Change (IGBP)

27 - 29 March, Tokyo, Japan

Contact: M & J International, 2210-2 Imajuka-cho, Asahi-ku, Yokohama 241, Japan; fax: 81 45 361 9681

ISY meeting

Space in the service of the changing earth

30 March - 5 April Munich, Germany

Contact: B Pfeiffer, ESA/ESTEC - ISY Office, Kerpleraan 1/P O Box 299, AG Noordwijk, Netherlands

IBC Technical Services in association with The Environment Council's Business and Environment Programme

Integrated Pollution Control - the lessons learnt

1 - 2 April Hotel Intercontinental, London W1

It is now a year since the new Integrated Pollution Control legislation became law. This meeting will provide a unique opportunity to learn from the HMIP (Her Majesty's Inspectorate of Pollution), from other regulatory bodies and from industry what progress has been made and what problems remain in operating within the new framework of Integrated Pollution Management. There will be opportunities to learn about the first attempts to utilise the concepts of Best Available Technology Not Entailing Excessive Cost (BATNEEC) and Best Practicable Environmental Options (BPEO).

The conference will be of interest to those whose existing plant will require authorisation over the next year or two, or to those planning to commission new plants which will be subject to IPC authorisation before they can be operated.

For further information and registration form, contact: IBC Technical Services Ltd, IBC House, Canada Road, Byfleet, Surrey KT14 7JL; tel: 071 631 3214

Global Warming International Centre

Global Warming - A call for international coordination, Third international conference on the scientific and policy issues facing all governments

6 - 9 April Illinois, USA

Contact: PO Box 5275, Woodbridge, Illinois 60517-0275 USA; tel: 708 910 1551

UK Geophysical Assembly - 16

6 - 10 April Edinburgh University

UKGA will be held jointly with EGS-17, the meeting of the European Geophysical Society

There is a variety of registration fees depending on the numbers of days to be attended and whether a member of JAG, the Joint Association for Geophysicists. Students can also claim a reduced fee.

Registration forms are available from UKGA LOC, University of Edinburgh, J C M B Room 6314, King's Buildings, Edinburgh EH9 3JZ; tel & fax: 031 650 4918.

International Environment 1992 - Exhibition and Conference

10 - 12 May Wembley, London

This international conference is designed to offer a forum for specialists and other to share informed and practical advice. The conference programme has been designed to give delegates a wide choice of pertinent topics.

Conference sessions include ones on Sensors, Waste Management, the Indoor Environment, and the final Plenary Session produces a "Declaration" for presentation to the DTI for international discussion.

Contact: Mrs E Davies, Labnate Ltd, 12 Alban Park, Hatfield Road, St Alban's Herts AL4 0JJ; tel: 0727 831337
for the exhibition, contact B Hewson at the same address

Remote Sensing Society

Climate Research and Earth Observation

May date and venue to be confirmed

Contact: The Admin. Secretary, The Remote Sensing Society, Dept of Geography, University of Nottingham, Nottingham NG7 2RD; tel: 0602 587611

Remote Sensing Society

ATSR: The Instrument and Data Processing

June Date and venue to be confirmed

Contact: as above

UN Conference on Environment and Development

1 - 12 June, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil

VII Dundee Summer School in Remote Sensing

Remote Sensing and Climate Change

19 August - 8 September Dundee, UK

Contact: R Vaughan, Dept of APEME, University of Dundee, Dundee DD1 4HH

OTHER NEWS

The International Conference on An Agenda of Science for Environment and Development into the 21st Century was held in Vienna, 24-9 November 1991 (ASCEWD 21).

The meeting was convened by the International Council of Scientific Unions in cooperation with several other organisations and a copy of the final Conference Statement can be obtained from:

Mr M Millward, ICSU Assistant Executive Director, 51 Blvd de Montmorency, 75016--Paris, France; tel: 33 1 4525 0329

UK National Plan for the Global Energy and Water Cycle Experiment (GEWEX)

Copies of this report containing proposals for the UK contribution to the above international programme are available from:

Dr K Browning, Dept of Meteorology, University of Reading, 2 Early Gate, Whiteknights Road, Reading, RG6 2AU; tel: 0734 875123 X 4283

Environmental Help for Management

The Conservation Foundation has launched a new information service aimed at helping those with new found environmental responsibilities. This service is part of the Environmental Managers Group, an initiative designed to keep managers abreast of the wide variety of information related to practices, processes, training and legislation on environmental issues. The scheme also offers a free legal service.

Further information can be obtained from David Shreeve, Conservation Foundation, 1 Kensington Gore, London SW7 2AR; tel: 071 823 8842

INFORMATION

Several publications have come my way which may be of interest or use to EPG members. Below is a selective digest, along with contact addresses.

British Library Environmental Information Resources

Newsletter No 17 of the Science Reference and Information Service focuses on the many forms of environmental information the British Library has access to. In 1989 the British Library launched its Environmental Information Service as a centralised access point. They can be contacted on 071 323 7955, fax: 071 323 7954. No charges are made for short quick enquiries. SRIS Newsletter 17 features such topics as key environmental sources everyone should know about, environmental auditing, environmental legislation and also reviews some key publications.

SRIS Newsletter is available free from:

Marketing and Public Relations, The British Library Science Reference and Information Service, 25 Southampton Buildings, London WC2A 1AW.

IOP members are welcome to contact the Public Affairs Department when they are at Belgrave Square if they wish to look at the following publications:

IPCC Scientific Assessment, 1990

This Common Inheritance - one year on, 1991, DoEnv.

We also have a summary document of *Caring for the Earth - a strategy for sustainable living*, published by the UN Environment Programme, the World Wild Fund for Nature and the IUCN, the World Conservation Union. Copies of the full Document can be obtained from the World Conservation Centre, Avenue du Mont-Blanc, CH1196 Gland, Switzerland.

Young engineer for Britain

This competition, run by The Engineering Council announced in January that among the new prizes to be awarded this year were National Westminster Bank prizes totalling £2500 for projects that best investigate engineering solution to environmental problems.

Entries are invited from students aged 11-19 in schools, colleges and industry in the UK and must be in by 31 March.

Competition information and entry form available from Young Engineers for Britain, The Engineering Council, 10 Maltravers St, London WC2R 3ER

The Globe

This is a free publication put out by the UK Global Environment Research (GER) Office. The GER Office is jointly funded by all research councils and is based at Polaris House, North Star Avenue, Swindon SN2 1EU; tel: 0793 411734.

This page of news is all culled from the December 1991 issue, with thanks.

This issue carries a review of UK Paleostudies related to Global Change, funded by SERC and NERC. Programmes aim to gather information about past events which will assist in predicting the pattern future global change will take. Improving such knowledge should assist in determining whether observations of apparent changes over short timescales represent signal or just noise.

1993 will see a community meeting on the NERC Special Topic, *Paleoclimate of the last glacial/interglacial cycle*. NERC is also looking at the Geology of Global Change as part of the international *Terrestrial Initiative in Global Environmental Research*.

Archaeological research over the last 2000 years funded by SERC covers the period of man's greatest impact on the environment. The International Geosphere - Biosphere Programme, Past Global Changes (PAGES) is split roughly into two temporal streams: the last 2000 years and the glacial - interglacial cycles of the last several thousand years of the late quaternary. Dr J Pilcher of Queens University Belfast is on the Scientific Steering Committee. Research into the oceans and their role in climate change features in the IGBP Joint Global Ocean Flux Study, which will be coordinated with PAGES.

The European Science Foundation is running a European Paleoclimate Project.

The Inter-Agency Committee on Global Environment Change (IACGEC) is to present its second report in September 1992. The first section will review the issues and look at progress made in the UK on research into processes, whilst also covering international research in this field. The second section will look at the impacts and remedial measures. Input to this section will be determined by a workshop to be held in February.

Further information from David Brown at the UK GER Office.

The next issue of *Globe* will cover the invited papers to the IACGEC Seminar held in December at Imperial College. The December issue conveniently collects summaries from the five centres of environmental research who featured at the meeting:

Centre for the Study of Environmental Change, Lancaster University
Global Environment Research Center (GERC), Imperial College London
Environmental Change Unit, University of Oxford
Centre for Social and Economic Research on the Global Environment,
University of East Anglia & University College London
Cambridge Interdisciplinary Environmental Centre

The United Nations Environment Programme has established an Information Unit on Climate Change.

Contact: Frances Barron, UNEP / IUCC, Palais des Nations, 1211 Geneva 10, Switzerland; tel: 758 25 27/34

Manchester Polytechnic has recently launched a *Global Climate Change Information Programme*, a joint venture between the Dept of the Environment and the Atmospheric Research and Information Centre.

Contact: M J Edwards, ARIC, Dept of Env & Geog Studies, Manchester Polytechnic, Chester St, Manchester M1 5GD; tel: 061 247 1593

TWO MAJOR ENVIRONMENTAL PHYSICS SPACE MISSIONS LAUNCHED

The summer of 1991 saw the launch of two important space missions, both dedicated to the study of aspects of the global climate system. This was the culmination of over a decade of work for hundreds of scientists and engineers in Britain and around the world. Both missions involved British groups in the development of advanced spectroscopic remote sensing instruments for studies of the atmosphere and the oceans.

The first mission is the European project ERS-1. The UK, through the British National Space Centre was a participant in the ERS programme, developed by the European Space Agency. ERS-1 was launched on an Ariane rocket in July into a polar orbit at an altitude of about 780 km. It carries a set of instruments designed to make quantitative physical measurements of the state of the ocean surface, the main payload comprising a number of radar systems designed to measure winds and waves at the ocean surface. Successfully developed by Marconi Space Systems, one of these radars is the Synthetic Aperture Radar.

The SERC acted as prime funder for another of the instruments: the Along Track Scanning Radiometer (ATSR). This is a multi-channel, multi-look infrared radiometer intended to make extremely high accuracy measurements of the temperature of the global ocean surface. Spectral channels at 1.6, 3.6, 11 and 12 microns are included in ATSR, which also employs photoconductive infrared detectors, cooled by single stage Stirling cycle Coolers. Using a simple conical scan technique, the design allows for each pixel of ocean surface to be viewed twice, through two different air masses. This allows us to eliminate the effect of absorptions by the intervening atmosphere on the radiance detected from the ocean surface. The ATSR instrument and the Stirling cycle Coolers were designed, developed, tested and delivered to ESA by a consortium led by RAL, which includes Oxford University, the Met Office, British Aerospace, and groups in both Australia and France.

To date the ATSR is producing remarkable data of very high quality at all wavelengths, from which global ocean surface temperatures, of critical importance to global climate research, are being derived.

In September 1991 NASA launched the second space mission: the Upper Atmosphere Research Satellite (UARS). This project is directed at the study of the Earth's stratosphere and mesosphere, and in particular the investigation of the physics and chemistry which determines the global ozone cycle and balance in the stratosphere. A battery of 10 novel and advanced instruments have been developed for UARS, which collectively provides the comprehensive suite of measurements of atmospheric constituents, temperature and dynamics which are needed to test modern theories of the ozone cycle. One of these instruments, the Advanced Stratospheric and Mesospheric Sounder (ISAMS) was provided by British groups. For a second, the Microwave Limb Sounder (MLS), UK teams developed some key hardware for this US-Jet Propulsion Lab-led project.

ISAMS operates between 4 and 17 microns, over 20 channels. Some of the channels are dedicated to identifying particular molecules while others are designed to detect radiation from wider spectral features, eg volcanic emissions. ISAMS detectors are cooled by UK Stirling cycle Coolers also. ISAMS measures the stratospheric concentrations on a global basis of, among others, the following molecules: O₃, H₂O, NO and NO₂, HNO₂ and CH₄. The experiment has produced excellent results so far, far surpassing previous data. Oxford University leads the project with close support from RAL, British Aerospace and Reading University. Measurements of O₃, H₂O and the ozone-destroying ClO are being made by MLS, a microwave heterodyne radiometer.

More details of these exciting and successful projects will appear in the coming months and years in many journals. Many people have been unstinting in their commitment to the projects. UK researchers in higher education and industry are working closely together to develop some very intricate and complex advanced instrumentation. These are now producing data which is going to prove of enormous value in improving our understanding of the Earth's global environment.

This is work that provides the most challenging physics and engineering, and is also of direct benefit to mankind. We need more young physicists to enter this exciting field: if you need more information on how to do this please contact the Environmental Physics Group or the author at RAL.

Professor John Harries Associate Director APS, Head of Space Science Dept
Rutherford Appleton Laboratory

ESA's Remote Sensing Satellite ERS-1 successfully launched on 16 July 1991. The satellite weighs over 2 tonnes and is over 6m in length. The payload instrument can be seen to the left of this diagram, and the solar array, which rotates as the satellite circles the Earth, is on the right.

Figure courtesy Rutherford Appleton Laboratory

INSTITUTE OF PHYSICS ENVIRONMENTAL PHYSICS GROUP

Summer Visit
Wednesday 26 June

Department of Physiology & Environmental Science
University of Nottingham
Faculty of Agricultural and Food Sciences
Sutton Bonington (near Loughborough)

The visit will see research on Environmental Science in the Faculty.

Tropical Crops Research Unit

Studies of the responses of tropical crops to Climate Change are in progress, using a computer controlled suite of glasshouses to simulate tropical climates. The objective is to determine the effects of particular climate conditions on crop growth and yield, particularly CO₂ concentration, temperature and water balance. The 1991 crops will be sorghum and groundnut.

Dr S Azam-Ali, Dr J A Clark (Funding: UK Overseas Development Administration)

Responses of Trees to Ozone Pollution

The consequences of ozone pollution for the growth and development of deciduous trees are being studied using open-top chambers operated by computer control. The responses will be measured in terms of their effects on leaf area duration and plant development in young apple trees. Controlled concentrations of ozone are designed to compare a 'clean' atmosphere with ambient ozone and an elevated concentration.

Professor M H Unsworth, Dr C J Wright, Dr J Wiltshire (Funding: DOE & NERC)

Responses of Legumes to Ozone Pollution

The effects of ozone on french bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris*) are being investigated using open-top chambers to enclose areas of crop. Five levels elevated of O₃ pollution will be controlled by computer, and the crop development and yield monitored throughout the crop duration.

Dr J J Colls, Dr G Sanders (Funding: DOE & CEC)

There will also be an opportunity to see posters of other Environmental Science research in progress in the Faculty, and a display of commercial equipment for measurement and control in the Environmental Science is also being arranged.

ENERGY FROM THE ENVIRONMENT — THE RENEWABLE ALTERNATIVE

Sir Hermann Bondi provided a thought-provoking start by challenging the meeting's title. We need all energy sources, he said. The renewables should not be regarded as alternatives, but essential for the whole picture, he said.

In our considerations, we must look at the global picture. Whereas in days of old it was the heavy industries that used energy intensively, now it was the knowledge-based industries. Energy efficiency is in itself a major factor, and should be achievable to a high degree in the developed nations. Arguably the biggest issue in developing nations is the removal of famine. This means using energy, and a lot of it. For the developing countries the energy must be technically simple, and it must be cheap - but the cost must include the environmental cost.

Dr Taylor from the Energy Technology Support Unit gave an impressive overview of the state of renewable energies in the UK, hence automatically omitting a number of renewable energies. The ETSU review of energy should be completed by the end of 1991.

Wind Energy

Large resources of wind energy exist offshore, according to David Millborow of National Wind Power. The St Helena wind generator should be in place in two years.

Wind energy is attractive in that there is plenty available, there is no pollution and it does not need to be sited near water. However, it is visually obtrusive, and generally needs to be installed close to the load, ie, town or city using the power generated.

Developments involve either a few high output devices or a larger number of lower output devices. Other factors to take into account include location - whether in remote or densely populated areas - and whether it is intended to be an ancillary source or the main source of electrical power.

Energy from the oceans

Dr Alastair Johnson, Marconi, gave an original and humorous review of ocean thermal energy conversion (OTEC), including two interesting descriptions of why neither government nor industry in the UK took a substantial interest in this during the 1980s.

OTEC requires a temperature difference between the top oceanic layer and a lower layer. This is readily available because of solar heating and the movement of cold water from polar regions. Johnson noted that despite this resource being related to tropical and subtropical areas, its use could be global. The thermal resource of the oceans is such that whether the sun shines or the wind blows, the energy source is always there, varying only over an annual cycle.

The French were the first to do work on OTEC in the late 19th Century, even building a demonstration plant in the 1930s. The Tokyo Electric Power Company built a land-based OTEC plant in the 1970s and '80s right on the equator, on the former Australian/New Zealand/British condominium of Nauru, developing net power until severe storms destroyed the cold water pipe.

Since 1979, work has been carried out at the Natural Energy Lab in Hawaii. A subsidiary benefit of OTEC is that the cold water is nutrient-rich, making it possible to grow plants not normally possible. The aqua-culture carried out

here - the growing of algae and strawberries, tomatoes, celery etc for sale - show the potential for adding to the local economy in other important ways.

There are challenges for various technologies, including developing reliable heat exchangers for reliably pumping up the cold water. A major breakthrough in OTEC work has been the use of aluminium heat-exchangers developed by GEC and Alcan of Canada. In the Caribbean there is a proposal to enhance the OTEC power by using the already warm surface water as a solar collector under a plastic sheet to further raise its temperature.

Biomass

Dr Jonathan Scurlock, Biology Dept, Kings College, reminded us that 14% of the world's total energy is derived from biomass and this rises to 35% in the developing world. Biomass energy is well-suited to straightforward conversion processes, eg wood and sundry wastes to electrical power generation. The high technology comes in when clean and efficient burning of the biomass is necessary. High temperatures allow complete combustion, leaving relatively little waste.

There is potential for producing non-trivial contribution to power demands, both globally and locally. It can be integrated into land-use and possibly into the stabilisation of employment, eg conversion from production of certain food-crops to production of fuel crops.

Sweden is very active in this following its decision to phase out nuclear power stations. The UK has become noticeably more involved in the last year.

Wave Energy

Dr Trevor Whitaker, Queen's University, Belfast, works on one of only three wave energy devices in the world which are operational. In his dynamic and exciting overview of wave energy, Whitaker focussed on this device, installed on the Scottish island of Islay, and the UK's only operational device. He compared the activities of the UK and Norway over the last two decades, referring especially to the Wells turbine, now the favoured design for wave energy plants.

Solar Energy

Dr Kirby, Ecogen, demonstrated in his wide-ranging talk that it is possible to build both efficiently and cheaply. He illustrated his talk with pictures of many of the innovative house designs, including several Council house schemes. With careful planning, the economic load is no greater than with the traditional house. He also introduced us to one of the first examples of a solar panel: the dorsal fins of a triceratops!

The Developing World

Dr Toby Harrison, the ODA, pointed out that simply to split the world into the developed and the developing was too simplistic a division. He endorsed Sir Hermann's point that we could not do without energy derived from fossil fuels and nuclear sources. Very large amounts of additional energy are likely to be needed to meet the world's needs in coming decades. The objectives in using renewables in the Third World should be to reduce fuel imports, aid the transition away from fossil fuels and to provide important services, eg power for hospitals.

He felt that designs for renewable energy schemes should be done in the developed world. Then and only then should the designs be taken out and the demonstration work done in the developing countries. Renewables have the potential to make a significant contribution to the energy equation in the developing world in the long term. A World Bank survey for the Less Developed Countries showed that their generating capacity would need nearly to double in

the decade 1989 - 1999. Before an organisation like the ODA could recommend a renewable energy scheme it needs criteria for viability.

What I would like to reinforce is that these renewable energies which are under scrutiny in Japan, the USA and throughout Europe depend for their success on high prices for traditional power, for example oil fuel as a source. The other major factor is the technical feasibility of these systems. The market for renewables is going to be a function of these two points, demand, financial resources and political acceptability coupled with human acceptability. The opportunities must take note of all these factors - and this I believe has been done in a number of cases. There will be a significant lead time for any major market.

In assessing opportunities, everyone will assign different priorities to each factor and assumptions will be made. One of the principle problems for renewable energies is the absence of a client industry for new technology plants. There is a need therefore for a "proxy customer" for the first demonstration plant. This is almost certainly where governments or international agencies have a vital role to play.

To summarise this round-up, there are four questions we should identify the answers to as we consider the future of a renewable energy scheme:

- * What is the market? This is a non-political question - nothing to do with market economies or centrally planned economies, but we do need to know our potential market before we move to spend money on R & D.
- * At what stage is the technology?
- * What is the environmental impact? As we have heard today, and it is difficult to over-emphasise, one man's environmental benefit is another's disadvantage.
- * Where is the UK? Now? And where are we going?

As a final comment, and very much paraphrasing Sir Hermann's opening remarks:

Don't think big, but do think total.

Don Lennard

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$$4.55 \times \frac{3}{2} = \frac{13.65}{2} = 6.825$$